

Effect of viral infected plant materials and filterable agents on biomethanation[†]

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Abstract : Biomethanation of common plant materials, both healthy and viral infected, was studied under anoxic conditions using inocula from different sources as well with filterable agents from viral infected plants. Biomethanation had always been found to be less with viral infected plants but the effect was not much. But with filterable agents, differential alterations or interferences in biomethanation were observed. The level of interaction may be organismic alloinhibition.

Keywords : Biomethanation, viral infection, organismic alloinhibition, filterable agent.

Introduction

The anaerobic digestion of biomass known as biomethanation has now been considered to be one of the best non-conventional source of energy. It is desirable to find ways and means to enhance biogas generation to make it effective and cost viable. Naturally, it demands the study of different aspects of biomethanation. Extensive studies on the different aspects of biomethanation were done by the authors¹⁻⁶. Acceleration or inhibition of biomethanation has been observed with different substrates or as a result of chemical or biological interactions of varied nature. This aspect has been the subject matter of interest and has been studied systematically in this laboratory¹⁻⁶ and others cited therein. In view of the importance of energy generation, attempts have been made to generate biogas from plant materials by different authors⁷⁻¹² without much success.

Inanimate interactions on biomethanation are well known. Biotic interactions particularly with bacteria and fungi have been studied more or less in broad spectrum^{13,14}. Effect of virus infection and interaction on plants have been studied by different workers like Carrington *et al.*¹⁵, Leisner *et al.*^{16,17}, Maule¹⁸, Ross¹⁹, Seron²⁰. Studies on the effect of viral filterable agent and viral infected sub-

strates on biomethanation has not been reported. So an attempt has been made to study the viral infected interactions on biomethanation, the results of which are described in this communication.

Experimental

Inocula from different sources were prepared in the way described earlier^{2,4,6}.

Preparation of viral filterable agent :

Filterable agent (CMV, Cucumber Mosaic Virus)²¹⁻²³ from infected leaves of Croton and Jatropha receiving severe infection viz. vein clearing and vein banding were collected from the natural population, crushed with carborandum powder, mixed with sterile water (1 : 1, w/v) and filtered through Whatman filter paper (No. 42). The filtrate was then passed through membrane filter (0.22 µm, Millipore, USA) to eliminate biotic and abiotic cell inclusions. The operation was done aseptically within a Klensoid Laminar flow apparatus. The filtrate containing the virus particles as filterable agent was centrifuged at 16000 r.p.m. The pellet thus formed was dispersed in 1 ml of sterile water and 0.1 ml of this solution was used in the experiment.

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Preparation of biomass :

Both normal and viral infected plant materials (*Croton bonplandianum*, *Jatropha gossypifolia*) collected from natural vegetation from Kalyani University Campus, were crushed and made into slurries with sterile water (1 : 1, w/v). 5 ml of the slurry containing 1 g plant material was dispensed in each vial (15 ml) for biomethanation. Vials were sealed and made anoxic by flushing argon for several minutes. The vials were then inoculated with 0.1 ml inoculum of a 10^5 dilution. The vials were argon flushed again and incubated at 37 °C. The whole operation was done aseptically within Klenzoid Laminar flow apparatus. For experiments with viral infected filterable agents, 0.1 ml of filterable agent prepared (described before) was inoculated at the time of experiment along with the inoculum.

Methane production (methane %) was measured as a function of time. Methane production from 1 ml gas from the headspace of the experimental vial was quantified using a Netal Gas Chromatograph utilizing a silica gel methane column and a hydrogen flame ionization detector. The results are means of at least triplicate experiments and always verified by at least a second set of experiments. The Gas Chromatograph was calibrated against a known standard of pure CH_4 (5.21% CH_4 in N_2 was used as 100% CH_4). N_2 (flow rate 30 ml/min) was used as a

carrier gas^{2,4,6}.

In all cases, the contents of the vials were rejected after each set of reading. Since the volumes at the headspace were kept constant in all the experimental sets, the percentage of methane can be considered to be roughly proportional to the percentage yield of methane in the biogas obtained by the digestion process.

Results and discussion

The results of biomethanation are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The results suggest a decrease in percentage yield of methane with viral infected plant materials compared to healthy plant materials. Only with cow dung as inoculum, the methane production with viral infected plant materials was virtually similar or marginally increased compared to those of the healthy plant materials. Naturally, infected plant materials had little to do with biomethanation process. Interference or differential alteration in methane yield had been found with addition of filterable agent. Severe interference in methane production had been observed with cow dung as inoculum for digestion of *Croton* or *Jatropha* leaves. With buffalo dung and goat dung inocula, interactions had been observed so as to emit methane at a lower potential. Interaction with piggery waste or poultry wash is less antagonistic to

Table 1. Effect of infection and filterable agent on the methane fermentation of *Croton bonplandianum* by cattle slurry

Substrates (Biomass)	Inoculum	Filterable agent	Percentage methane yield (days)					
			5	10	15	20	25	30
H.Pl.	Cow dung	-	40.5	54.5	56.0	35.4	31.8	27.0
I.Pl.		-	38.1	56.3	61.9	36.1	31.4	22.3
H.Pl.	Buffalo dung	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
H.Pl.		-	4.5	4.9	36.6	47.2	40.9	18.1
I.Pl.	Goat dung	-	2.8	16.3	19.0	27.2	3.6	1.8
H.Pl.		+	-	-	23.3	33.3	24.0	2.2
H.Pl.	Piggery wastes	-	47.0	64.2	66.6	69.0	60.1	42.8
I.Pl.		-	36.6	62.3	66.2	69.0	47.1	38.0
H.Pl.	Poultry wash	+	44.7	64.2	64.2	66.2	52.1	12.3
H.Pl.		-	15.4	61.9	65.7	63.8	35.2	11.4
I.Pl.	Poultry wash	-	8.5	61.9	55.2	52.8	52.3	28.0
H.Pl.		+	32.3	62.8	55.2	55.2	19.1	8.1
H.Pl.	Poultry wash	-	8.1	30.9	40.0	45.4	55.4	24.5
I.Pl.		-	2.9	3.8	41.8	39.1	17.2	16.3
H.Pl.		+	-	1.8	25.4	40.9	13.2	4.5

H.Pl. - Healthy plant, I.Pl. - Infected plant.

Table 2. Effect of infection and filterable agent on the methane fermentation of *Jatropha gossypifolia* by cattle slurry

Substrates (Biomass)	Inoculum	Filterable agent	Percentage methane yield (days)					
			5	10	15	20	25	30
H.Pl.	Cow dung	-	52.0	53.1	51.8	47.9	36.3	21.7
I.Pl.		-	50.1	55.0	47.7	49.0	39.9	28.4
H.Pl.	Buffalo dung	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
H.Pl.		-	10.1	16.6	41.3	58.0	51.1	18.1
I.Pl.		-	3.3	15.3	18.1	31.1	24.2	3.9
H.Pl.	Goat dung	+	-	9.6	28.1	21.2	7.9	7.0
H.Pl.		-	47.0	51.5	58.8	61.3	62.0	51.3
I.Pl.		-	40.4	41.9	49.9	55.0	57.9	42.0
H.Pl.	Piggary wastes	+	33.5	41.2	47.7	49.9	44.0	31.3
H.Pl.		-	24.0	41.1	50.0	55.5	51.3	29.9
I.Pl.		-	10.1	38.1	42.0	46.6	43.0	37.7
H.Pl.	Poultry wash	+	17.2	19.9	44.0	48.0	31.3	20.2
H.Pl.		-	12.2	34.0	47.0	51.2	59.7	41.4
I.Pl.		-	5.0	8.8	40.0	40.2	33.0	26.7
H.Pl.		+	2.9	7.7	18.9	31.3	47.7	34.4

H.Pl. – Healthy plant, I.Pl.– Infected plant.

biomethanation process. The level of interaction may be organismic alloinhibition but nothing specific can be predicted.

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